

Reproducible Archaeology Workshop

15 - 22 Oct 2021

Poll results

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What is your career stage? (1/2)

Postgraduate

Postdoctoral Researcher

Assistant Professor

Associate Professor

Professor

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Durham University
Archaeologists (1/8)

0 1 1

What is your career stage?
(2/2)

Other

0 %

Multiple-choice poll (Multiple answers)

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Durham University
Archaeologists (2/8)

0 1 1

What is your subdiscipline?
(1/3)

Landscape Archaeology

Environmental Archaeology

Archaeological Sciences - Materials

Paleopathology

Public Archaeology

What is your subdiscipline? (2/3)

Prehistoric Archaeology

Historical Archaeology

Classical Archaeology

Conservation and Museum Studies

Cultural Heritage Management

What is your subdiscipline?
(3/3)

Other

What software do you use for analysing your data?

**Where do you think you are on your
reproducibility journey? (1*=Complete beginner;
5*=Fully reproducible)**

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Durham University
Archaeologists (5/8)

0 1 2

Do you think your group would be supportive of moving towards a more reproducible approach?

Yes

No

Maybe

What do you find most daunting about reproducibility?

What could your first (or next) step be?

Consider data sharing

Consider methodologies

Consider analysis

Is there anything else you'd like to learn to help you with reproducibility?

- The intro part of the session was v
useful. Some basic strategies would
be useful

What is your career stage? (1/2)

Undergraduate

0 %

Postgraduate

32 %

Postdoctoral Researcher

48 %

Assistant Professor/Lecturer

4 %

Associate Professor/Senior Lecturer

4 %

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Archaeologists on Twitter (1/10)

0 2 5

What is your career stage? (2/2)

Professor

 4 %

Other

 8 %

If Career Stage was "Other", please give details

- Consultant in multi-disciplinary consultancy. Educated to PhD level.
- Why isn't CRM professional in here?
Indigenous archaeologists?
- Consulting archaeologist. Some government regulation work.

What is your subdiscipline? (1/3)

Landscape Archaeology

Environmental Archaeology

Archaeological Sciences - Materials

Paleopathology

Public Archaeology

What is your subdiscipline? (2/3)

Prehistoric Archaeology

Historical Archaeology

Classical Archaeology

Conservation and Museum Studies

Cultural Heritage Management

Multiple-choice poll (Multiple answers)

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Archaeologists on Twitter (3/10)

0 2 5

What is your subdiscipline?
(3/3)

Other

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Archaeologists on
Twitter (4/10)

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If subdiscipline was "Other", please give details

- Bioarchaeology and Dental Anthropology
- Digital Archaeology
- Evolution, Adaptation, and Zooarchaeology

What software do you use for analysing your data?

(1/2)

- R, Python, NetLogo
- Excel, SPSS
- Python, NLTK, HuggingFace, BERT, R, LibreOffice Calc
- R, GRASS GIS
- R, Python
- ArcGIS and/or QGIS
- QGIS, R, LibreOffice, Excel, PostgreSQL,
- R, QGIS,
- GIS, Visone, R, NetLogo
- R, Excel
- R, SQL
- R, ArcGIS, NetLogo
- QGIS, SPSS
- R
- R webmango drafgonfly Fuji imagej
- R, Excel
- R (in RStudio), Python (in VS Code), QGIS, GRASS GIS, SQL (in VS Code)
- R, Excel
- R, Rstudio, QGIS, LibreOffice
- QGIS, GRASS, R and satellite imagery cloud-computing

What software do you use for analysing your data?

(2/2)

platforms (eg. Google Earth Engine,
DIAS)

- ArcGIS, QGIS, MS excel, MS Access
- R
- R, Excel.
- R
- R

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Archaeologists on Twitter (6/10)

0 2 5

Where do you think you are on your reproducibility journey? (1*=Complete beginner; 5*=Fully reproducible)

Score: 3.6

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Archaeologists on Twitter (7/10)

0 2 5

Do you think your research group would be supportive of moving towards a more reproducible approach?

Yes

No

Maybe

What do you find most daunting about reproducibility?

(1/4)

- I find myself worrying that I have made simple errors in code that may keep others from being able to reproduce my analyses.
- Sometimes the methodological approaches need specific technological features that may not be accessible to all labs or research teams. The published methods may not be as specific as needed in order to reproduce the method or may be clear enough.
- The time it takes to make research properly reproducible
- It is not daunting.
- The extra time and effort spent on all the steps without any immediate benefits to one's work life and career (no extra points for being FAIR)
- Mainly that I have no idea how it applies, how it could be made to apply and why it's even desirable
- Not all data or software is open, not

What do you find most daunting about reproducibility?

(2/4)

all software is supported by the institute

- time consuming, not rewarded, not supported to do it by stakeholders/funding agencies
- Nothing. Its, frankly, a bare minimum standard. I understand *some* things are more difficult to reproduce (especially Experimental work where reproducing the individual acting as expert

can be nearly impossible to exactly mirror etc.), but as someone who works in a lab-science heavy part of archaeology, its expected of what I do.

- Programming languages have steep learning curves and are even more difficult to access if your current career path has gone a different direction.
- Providing the detail of data
- That the vast majority of isotopic

What do you find most daunting about reproducibility?

(3/4)

papers do not even mention reproducibility

- When switching between programs. And dealing with software such as webmango.
- Coding skills required
- Time investment + environmental impact from storing unnecessary data
- Providing raw data that you may want to use again.
- data publication
- Scarcity of documents and

guides to transform your dirty code into a more standard, clean or protocolary code ready to be published and shared (eg. as supplementary information).

- Finding a place for experience and interpretation.
- Nothing really. I guess there is an initial reluctance for being fully exposed but it's a sacrifice worth making!
- Are you talking about perspective of publishing scholar,

What do you find most daunting about reproducibility?

(4/4)

reviewer, or general observer in the reproducibility scene? I have a hard time justifying the time wasted testing reproducibility in different computer systems.

- How little it is valued by most archaeologists
- I don't find reproducibility daunting, I consider it an ethical responsibility.

What could your first, or next, step towards reproducibility be?

(1/3)

- Perhaps having others look at my code or trying it out before I publish it or make it open access.
- Contact between labs and facilities in order to get all the technical requirements to reproduce the method, and to clearly explain step by step how to apply it.
- Integrate reproducibility from the start of the next project, instead of at the end!
- I have made all of my analyses reproducible in the paper I published. I share both the original datasets and the R scripts.
- Try to replicate/rerun your own project from last year 😊 Document your project so undergrad students can replicate.
- Who knows. It's not really an aim I've ever considered
- I am already writing reproducible code
- Helping to standardize

What could your first, or next, step towards reproducibility be?

(2/3)

- some methods. By which I mean - zooarchaeology is lacking in experimental work that looks at... for example if horse whithers estimation can be used on deer or if we really do need to come up with a new methodology for that etc.
- Learning python, getting better at R including both stats and data manipulation, learning how to do gis in r... Overall spending more time
 - working with the languages. I currently upload all my data and code to repositories which are then associated with my articles and reports.
 - Open access my data
 - Partake in meta-analyses
 - ? Not sure
 - Getting more comfortable with coding, more familiar with Github
 - Learn Docker
 - Putting past projects online.
 - check permission rights for

What could your first, or next, step towards reproducibility be?

(3/3)

- online publication of dataset
- To share code and data even for the easiest or more explorative plot
- More standardized collection and reporting methods.
- I already commit my work to be fully reproducible. My challenge is now convince my coauthors and colleague to do the same!
- Reproducibility has to be more about validating findings rather than figures in a journal article.

It also needs to include trusted and validated documentation about the protocols for collecting data and sampling protocols, not just data analysis. Reviewers and editors need to actually value it and actually put effort into testing the code in order for it to succeed.

- Increasing awareness of the importance of reproducible research among peers

Is there anything else you'd like to learn to help you with reproducibility?

(1/3)

- no
- How to pitch reproducibility to managers and people in senior positions, who decide about one's career and jobs.
- No really
- Make steps in gui software more easily reproducible
- No.
- Couple thoughts: usually in a survey like this you want to define what you

mean by reproducibility in each section so dummies like me can remember. I think too that you are leaving folks out by only thinking of academics as generating reproducible archaeology. What about demographics? Crowd sourcing solutions to these problems? I've written a paper on this topic

Is there anything else you'd like to learn to help you with reproducibility?

(2/3)

and have an idea what I need to keep working on, but also know that there are many structural barriers to learning how to keep research reproducible or replicable. I hope this survey pans out for you but suspect you'll get a fairly biased sample..

- Not sure
- Learn more about the ethics of surrounding reproducibility, not all data can be publicly shared and I would like

to know more about best practice for when there are legitimate reasons you can try make things 100% open

- Not that I'm aware of at the moment
- formal code review to make sure it's in good shape to be published
- For R, using R Markdown. For other languages (JavaScript, Python), it would help to have some guidance on how to present

Reproducible Archaeology: Responses from Archaeologists on Twitter (10/10)

0 1 2

Is there anything else you'd like to learn to help you with reproducibility?

(3/3)

your code ready for publication and also some (archaeological) guidance on how to use the best of GitHub or similar platforms.

- Guidelines for peer reviewers to examine reproducibility of papers they review